

mosaic

MOSAIC co-creation methodology toolkit

Section 5: Prototyping.

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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1. Example of storyboard preparation facilitation guideline

Main expected outcomes:

- A detailed storyboard of the idea
- Integration of the “user’s journey” into the idea
- Improvement of the idea by adding “small innovations” to enhance the user’s experience.

0:00-0:10 – Welcome

Welcome to this new gathering and thanks for joining. My name is XXX and I will be your main facilitator today. Before we start, some housekeeping information:

- *(If food/drinks are available)* There is food available ..., please feel free to grab a coffee, drinks or something to eat at any time. We have also foreseen a long break in the middle of the meeting for you to enjoy the food and get some fresh air.
- If needed, emergency exits are...
- Toilets are...

0:10-0:20 – Introduction and icebreaker

General aim: In this meeting, we will start to give life and details to our idea, so it becomes more precise, clearer, and we may see new opportunities for innovation arising. Take a time to remember what happened two weeks ago, ask them if they had new thoughts during the last days.

Objectives:

- To transform the idea into a clear and precise project.
- To design a first version of a storyboard

Icebreaker

But first, let’s wake up! Find someone in the room you don’t know very well, and make a pair. Now, think about that sentence: “in the past, I am proud I have made...”. What have you made or built, you personally? A model of a plane? Your own house? A playmobile castle for a child? A knitted jumper? A painting, a clay pot? A paper origami? It has to be a real object you made whether it is a giant construction or a pasta necklace – you cannot say that you “build your marriage” in that exercise! You now have five minutes to remind each other who you are, what your name and your occupation are, and to share the thing you made in the past.

0:20-1:00 – Storyboards

Our first step will be to detail a storyboard of your idea. Have you already identified a typical user for your idea? Is that a 35-year-old manager? A 30-year-old parent with their child? A 70-year-old person living on the outskirts of the city? If this is not clear yet, take a moment to define together a primary user. Remember it does not have to be your only user, your idea may benefit a lot of other people! However, that person should be a typical user who will strongly benefit from your idea. This person is now our hero, and we will describe their journey and their story. *(If undefined, take a moment to clarify the user with the group.)*

Now, let's build the storyboard. This storyboard is a little story of how our hero uses your product or service, with several episodes. You are going to work in pairs. (*Make pairs, help participants if needed. The same pairs as the previous icebreaker would be fine, if you feel they worked well*). Each pair has those paper sheets comprising a frame to draw and a few lines to write.

Let's start with the first team! (*Turn to the first pair*): What is the initial situation? Before the user uses the service, where are they, with whom, in which situation? What day/time is it? What are they doing, where are they going, how do they feel, what do they need? It's up to you to choose a typical example that seems relevant. You may draw (in a simple, even symbolic way if you wish) the situation and write a few words to describe it.

Next group: your turn to add an episode. You can add an episode after this first one, or before – if you think something important needs to happen before. So, what is the first interaction with the product/service? Do they see it, hear it? Please detail the following episode of the story...

Next group: now, it's up to you to add an episode, wherever you wish: at the beginning, after, or even in between the two existing episodes. You can progress in the use of the interaction, or you can detail an element, add something to the product/service, to the way it is used... But it has to be described as one additional episode. For now, we are using these paper storyboards to take quick notes with doodling and a few sentences. After this meeting, you will be able to design a much prettier and more comprehensive one. You may take more time to draw and write, or you may paste pictures from magazines or from the internet, and write your episodes with a computer.

Next group: what would you add to this story? Etc.

1:00-1:10 – Coffee break + Document

An important aspect that we need to keep in mind is that we need to document this process. We may keep notes and testimony from our works in various ways. You have here a Word document, that you may fill in during or after this meeting. You may paste here some pictures, add some videos or some sound recordings – if you prefer to speak rather than to write. But it is important that each of you leave an element, an impression, a memory from this meeting. The guiding question may help you to write a paragraph or record a testimony. You can already start doing this during the break if you wish, or at the end of this meeting, or later during the week. Please always write your name or initials after each answer, so we can see the multiplicity of the authors. To start with, take pictures of the storyboard to keep for later!

1:10-1:30 – Reflect

Take a moment to discuss the current storyboard. Is it comprehensive enough? Do you see opportunities to enrich it? In particular, are there elements we could add or change to make the service provided even better, to make the hero's journey even better? Sometimes, great innovations come from tiny details that truly change people's lives. Do you see any tiny detail we could improve here? (*Leave space if some participants wish to share their thoughts or reactions*).

01:30-01:40 Wrap-up

Thank you so much for your participation! A few things to do in the upcoming two weeks (*If there is extra time, use it for documentation*):

- Write answers in the diary, document the process as much as possible.
- Start thinking about this whole process described in the storyboard: where are the most important points, the most important elements? You can use the questions sheet to reflect.

2. Example of light prototyping facilitation guideline

0:00-0:05 – Welcome

Welcome to this new gathering and thanks for joining. My name is XXX and I will be your main facilitator today. Before we start, some housekeeping information:

- *(If food/drinks are available)* There is food available ..., please feel free to grab a coffee, drinks or something to eat at any time. We have also foreseen a long break in the middle of the meeting for you to enjoy the food and get some fresh air.
- If needed, emergency exits are...
- Toilets are...

Also introduce the maker space staff that will be supporting the group.

0:05-0:10 – Icebreaker (optional, you may skip it to keep more time for the tour of the maker space)

Before the session: gather a wide range of materials and tools from the maker space: a piece of cardboard, an elastic band, an electronic board, a wire, a screwdriver, other tools... There should be more materials and tools than the number of participants. Put all these elements on a table and ask all participants to look at them, and then pick up one material or tool.

Tell them to look at the material or tool they have chosen. What are its characteristics? Is it solid, flexible, cheap, expensive, precise, handy, sharp, reusable...? Tell them they have one minute to think to build their own sentence, on the model: “I am like this [material] because it is [characteristic] like me”. For example: “I am like this wrench because it is adaptable like me”. “I am like this nail because it is shiny like my my nail varnish”. If they find no common point with their item, they are allowed to switch to “I am unlike this [material] because it is [characteristic] and I am not!!!”. Have all of them say their sentence to the group.

0:10-0:25 – Tour and review of available materials

With the maker space staff, have a tour of the space: look at the various tools (laser cutter, sticker maker, 3D printer etc.), and most importantly look at the various materials: wood, metal, plastic, cardboard, textiles, rubber, electronics, wool, sticker, etc. It’s important to show participants the diversity of materials and raise their “appetite” for manipulating and using these materials. Notice any interest being shown by participants.

0:25-0:35 – Back to the storyboard

Ask all participants to review the storyboards. Are there any thoughts that came to them since the last meeting? If there is a need to detail the storyboard a bit more, participants can do this now. However, you may also use the prototyping time to detail the idea. (Example: in the “Places for people” group, participants may find it difficult to define the activities available in the meeting place. But if they are building a model of the place, they may happily add all the elements they would dream about (a swing, a tea room, a ping pong table, plenty of books and comfortable sofas, Hi-fi for classical music, a dancefloor for pop choreography...). Building and adding elements to a visual model may be much more joyful and simple than having to imagine it all from nothing. Unless needed, this step should be very quick: a mere reminder of the service created.

0:35-0:50 – What will we prototype?

Announce the next steps: we are now going to build a prototype for the service they designed. A prototype is a simple, low-fidelity representation of the service, or of a part of the service. It will have us design the service in greater detail. Many different things can be prototyped in various ways:

- An object (with simple cardboard, or wood shaped by a laser cutter, or any other available materials)
- A building (through a model in cardboard, wood, or a Lego construction)
- An app (through wireframes, with a wooden frame imitating a phone shape, and paper to draw the various screens)
- Any electronic device or automated element (through Arduino, Makey Makey, or other elements from the maker space).
- A content or a programme (through a movie shot with a smartphone, using actors or toys/dolls for characters)

Ask them to review their service from the storyboard, and to **list all the various things that could be prototyped** (they should not yet worry about *how* they will be prototyped):

- Specific objects used in the created service
- Places and buildings
- Computer/Smartphone app or other interactions
- Signposts in the street, road marking, etc.
- Contents inside a hub or a building
- Organization of people (for example: if we need various actions from various kinds of people, we can model it using toy characters in cardboard, playmobile or other materials).

In discussion with the group, come to an agreement about which element(s) will be prototyped. should aim to choose:

- The element(s) that embodies the core value of the idea
- The elements that are critical to the success of the idea

Depending on the group dynamics, you may want everyone to work on the same prototype, or several small groups to develop several prototypes. This will also depend on the prototype: if it is quite simple, 4 people working on it is more than enough. If it is complex and made of several sub-parts, it may require effort from everyone.

Note: If participants are unsure about what to prototype, it is useful to come back to the question sheet (at the end of the day diary) and have participants reflect on some of the following:

- What does our idea need to be successful?
- What seems to be a critical element for the idea?
- How can we make it easy to use, simple and reliable?
- What could increase its impact, help more people, make it more efficient?
- How can we ensure people will actually use it?
- What part of the idea is likely to work well? Where will the issues most probably come from?
- Are there some ethical issues linked to the idea? Some social or political issues? Are there some acceptability issues?

0:50 – 1:50 Making

Next, you have to determine *how* you will prototype.

- The materials: With the help of the maker space staff, orient the group towards materials that could be used for their prototype. You may suggest a mix of classic materials (e.g. cardboard wood) and less usual ones (e.g. textiles, silk paper, toys, fruits...). Creative materials often open the imagination of participants, which is beneficial to the service created. If some people are attracted to specific materials (e.g. sewing), take advantage of it and try to make use of everyone's skills and tastes. Don't hesitate to throw in some funny elements to bring some humour and some pleasure to the activity.
- The type of representation: Try to frame the ambition of the prototype. Some elements will be complex or detailed (for example: details of the road markings, activities in the meeting place...), while others will only be represented in a very symbolic way (e.g. Colours to represent if a service is open or closed). A prototype too simple may be boring to make, and a too ambitious one will discourage participants. If necessary, the maker space staff should be able to help you find the right level of ambition.

Have participants start making and building, joyfully. Your role will be mainly to check:

- When building the prototype, new questions will arise as it will force participants to define the service with a lot more precision. Whenever facilitation is needed, you may step in to frame a conversation, give space to a short debate or launch a quick brainstorming.
- If one or several participants are merely waiting on the side, try to "reactivate" them. This may be done by integrating them to the on-going task, or by giving them small side missions they will perform on their own, and add to the prototype at the end. (e.g. Design a sticker that will be made and added to the prototype at the end).

1:50 – 2:00 Wrap-up

Acknowledge together the progress and congratulate everyone for their work. The prototype is probably unfinished:

- Some parts may be finished at home.
- Other parts will need to be done in the maker space.

Plan together the upcoming work to have the prototype finished in the next two weeks.

Invite all participants to fill in the diary for today's session. This should be done as homework

- unless they prefer to do it right away.

3. Example of facilitation guidelines for feedback collection event preparation

Main objectives of the meeting:

- Finalise invitations of potential users of the innovation (groups are in charge of inviting people they want to get feedback from) - you can use a flyer for this.
- Decide who will present the idea and start preparing the presentation.
- Plan how the group wants to run the drop-in session (e.g., who will be there talking to people and how will feedback be collected?).

Introduction to meeting

- Summarise all prototype key aspects you have worked on so far, with the help of the group.
- Ask the group to reflect on key aspects of the prototype:
 - o Invite the group to reflect upon and collectively identify up to two key aspects of the prototype that could be important to further explore. Start working on them one by one, or split them in two groups if you have enough participants and ask them to focus on one aspect each.
 - o Key aspects of the prototype the group could focus on could include: a specific service, a business plan, a specific type of usage, connections with external elements that might impact the usage of the innovation, any critical element of the idea that they may have been forgotten, etc.
 - o If it can be of help, remind them the list of guiding questions we had provided in the previous script:
 - What does our idea need to be successful?
 - What seems to be a critical element for the idea?
 - How can we make it easy to use, simple and reliable?
 - What could increase its impact, help more people, make it more efficient?
 - How can we ensure people will actually use it?
 - What part of the idea is likely to work well? Where will the issues most probably come from?
 - Are there some ethical issues linked to the idea? Some social or political issues? Are there some acceptability issues?

Main working blocks:

About inviting “users” to the event / feedback collection:

- Do a quick mapping of specific target audiences that could be interesting to invite to test the innovation. I.e. supermarket customer, parents bringing kids to school, etc. etc. Think about concrete ways these people could be invited to the event and set up clear tasks on who invites who.
- Be clear that the success of the event also depends on them and that they should not expect “us” to make all the invitations and bring people. The city will do its best to help but they are also responsible for getting people to come to the event. They can invite friends, neighbours, colleagues etc. Anyone they think can give feedback on the idea.

- Plan other feedback collecting activities before the event. Explain to participants that if they wish so, they are welcome to organise themselves in going to specific places to collect feedback from people/audiences they consider interesting.
- Try to narrow down a few specific questions that the testing/collecting feedback should answer. Rather than “do they like it?”, it should focus on key aspects that could be improved or just better adapted to the audience.
- You can also invite participants to try and imagine possible questions that external users might ask them when looking at the prototype. Try anticipating questions and think of possible answers.

About presenting the idea at the event:

- At the beginning of the event each group will have 10 minutes to present the idea to the guests.
- Important: distribute tasks and responsibilities. Who presents? Even better if this is something shared by all.
- Some ideas on creating a presentation/pitch: <https://www.designkit.org/methods/create-a-pitch.html>
- The rest of the event will be organised on a drop-in basis, meaning that people can come whenever they like and someone from each team should be there to greet them at their table: present the prototype/idea, talk to them and collect feedback.

About collecting feedback at event:

Each team is welcome to develop their own protocol to collect feedback and will know which aspects of the prototype need digging into. However, it’s important to define your objectives: start by clarifying your goals for the prototype test. What specific aspects do you want to evaluate? Having clear objectives will guide your testing process.

The teams are encouraged to be as creative as they like during the testing process, you might not only consider talking about the idea, but also showing visuals, simulating a user experience, role playing etc.

Questions one can ask the potential users

1. General Feedback:

- What are your overall impressions of the prototype?
- Did the prototype meet your expectations?
- Is there anything you particularly liked or disliked about the prototype?

2. Specific Features and Functionality:

- What did you think about [specific feature]? How well did it work for you?
- Did you find all the necessary options or functionalities you expected?
- Were there any missing features or functionalities that you think should be included?

3. Visual Design and Layout:

- Did the visual design of the prototype appeal to you?
- Was the layout and organization of elements intuitive and easy to follow?
- Were there any visual elements that were distracting or confusing?

4. Suggestions for Improvement:

- Based on your experience, what improvements or changes would you recommend?

- Are there any additional features or functionalities you would like to see?
- How could the prototype better meet your needs or expectations?

5. Future Usage and Adoption:

- How likely would you be to use this product or service in the future?
- Are there any barriers or concerns that might prevent you from using it?
- Do you think this prototype would be valuable or useful to others?